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Qualitative Assessment of the 7S Program using the 7S Audit Checklist in Kasiglahan Village National High School

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Abstract: The research aims to assess and create awareness of the 7S Program with a systematized approach to organizing work areas, setting rules and standards, practicing self-discipline as a way of life, and maintaining safety in the workplace at Kasiglahan Village National High School. An exploratory method of research was used to gather relevant data that can be used for the 7S Program and to investigate how effective the Program is at Kasiglahan Village National High School. The 7S Program was implemented in the school. 7S Audit checklist was used to validate the effectiveness of the Program. The impact of the Program helps the school to create awareness of the 7S Program with a systematized Approach to organize work areas, set rules and standards, practice self-discipline as a way of life, and maintain Safety in the workplace. The study focuses on assessing the 7S Program using 7S Audit Checklist to the 33 different offices in Kasiglahan Village National High School, Rodriguez Rizal. A 7S Program helps to create awareness of basic concepts of the 7S Methodology of good housekeeping; implement and apply the 7S Program in the workplace, enhances Safety and makes a pleasant workplace, helps in work efficiency; and removes waste from the workplace. The researchers aim to validate the 7S program using the 7S Audit Checklist and to ensure a sound and systematic approach to improving working conditions by concentrating on maintaining the discipline needed to efficiently and effectively discharge its tasks and functions at Kasiglahan Village National High School.

Keywords: 7S audit checklist, qualitative, red tag, safety, systematize

1.1 Introduction

The 7S Program is one of the organization's most widely adopted techniques today to sustain the pursuit of Quality Management Systems. 7S Program is an expanded version of the 5S of Good Housekeeping. 7S stands for Sort, Systematize, Sweep, Standardize, Safety, Sustain, and Spirit. 7S Program is a systematized approach to Organizing work areas, setting rules and standards, practicing self-discipline as a way of life, and maintaining Safety in the workplace. A healthy workplace is believed to result in a safer, more efficient, and more productive implementation of procedures and processes. Beyond this, it also helps establish the framework and discipline required to pursue other continuous improvement initiatives successfully. Because of this, Kasiglahan Village National High School has implemented the 7S Program to ensure a sound and systematic approach to improving working conditions by concentrating on maintaining the discipline needed to efficiently and effectively discharge its tasks and functions. It is intended to optimize the physical workspace for efficiency and effectiveness by identifying and storing the items used, maintaining orderliness and cleanliness in the area, and sustaining the new order to ensure the safety of the teachers, students, and stakeholders in the most efficient manner.

The 7S Program supports the school in consolidating a workplace for efficiency, minimizing unnecessary waste, and optimizing quality and productivity through intermittent monitoring of the workplace. When successfully implemented and monitored, it would result in a vast efficiency enhancement, a tidy working environment, a reduction of unnecessary hazardous materials, a reduction in defects, and an increase in employee satisfaction.

2.1 Literature

Implementing 5S Methodology: The First Step Toward Workplace Efficiency

5S is the perfect tool to identify the first improvement projects in your company to eliminate waste. Although sometimes viewed as a housekeeping technique, it is an innovative management system that helps people think lean, paving the way for adopting Lean principles in the organization. Understanding the 5S Methodology is one of the foundations of Six Sigma principles and can be highly beneficial for organizations of all kinds.

HRMO holds Seminar on 7S's of Good Housekeeping

There used to be 5S's, but now that the practice has been updated to 7S's, the Human Resources Management Office likewise had to keep up with the times by organizing for LGU employees a newly updated seminar.

The 7S's of Good Housekeeping was held on October 10 at the Balon Bayambang Events Center, with all departments, units, and agencies well represented. (Yes, there are LGU employees detailed in various locally based national agencies.) Productivity Toolbox Trainer Ben A. Donglayan of the Regional Tripartite Wages and Productivity Board (San Fernando City, La Union) was tapped to lecture on 7S's.

The seminar aims to instill a greater sense of cleanliness, orderliness, and a positive workplace attitude to deliver a more effective and efficient service to the public. As HRMO head Nora Zafra puts it, "The seminar is intended to give employees knowledge on how to make their workplace cleaner and safer and their job simpler and more satisfying."

According to Donglayan, the 7S's are:

- Sort – Identifying and eliminating unnecessary items in the workplace
- Systematize – Arranging necessary items in good order for use
- Sweep – Cleaning your workplace and equipment
- Standardize – Maintaining a high standard of good housekeeping

- Safety – Maintaining a safe workplace
- Self-discipline -Doing things spontaneously without being told or ordered
- Sustain – Continuing 7s activities to achieve consistently good results

Juran and De Feo (2018) state that lean manufacturing is a technique of optimizing organizational systems by eliminating waste within them: anything that does not add value to the customer or the organization is considered waste. Further, they contend that developing a lean organization includes delivering products and services by using less of everything: less waste, less human effort, less manufacturing space, less outlay of tools, less inventory, less engineering time to develop a new product, and less motion.

The 5S Methodology encompasses creating a culture of a neat workplace. This includes removing anything that is not required in the workplace, sorting tools and materials, and always keeping the floor clean. Therefore, there is a high possibility that waste, such as product and inventory defects, could be eradicated when these two techniques are integrated.

A Lean 7S methodology framework to improve efficiency and organizational performance: A review study in an SME organization

Mahlaha (2020) The Efficiency and Quality in Manufacturing Business are some of the key differentiators between competing entities in the business environment and the marketplace. Therefore, improving efficiency and quality of means of production or service standards is one of the main obstacles confronting South African Small-Medium enterprises (SMEs) and other firms globally. Lean Approach techniques and methodologies are efficiency and process management Systems adapted largely from the Toyota Production System (TPS). The lean approach is a gradual transformation overall work environment. Generally, the Lean Approach is regarded as a set of tools to aid the detection and Eradication of wastes in the processing system. 7S Lean Methodology, which any scope organization could apply, is derived from five Japanese lean 5s Methodology; Sort, set in order, Shine, standardize, and sustain, extended by Safety as well as spirit in recent years. This Methodology aids the organization in the work environment for effectiveness and reduction of hindrances in processes. Also, it enhances quality standards throughout, by scrutinizing a prearranged work environment.

2.2 Statement Of The Problem

Generally, the study aimed to Assess the 7S Program in the Kasiglahan Village National High School. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

- Teacher Respondents
- Gender;
- Age;
- Length of Service; and
- Highest Educational Attainment?

How effective is the 7S Program as assessed by faculty members and evaluators using the 7S Audit Checklist in terms of:

- Sorting
- Systematizing

- Sweeping
- Standardizing and
- Sustainability

3.1 Statistical Analysis of Data

The following statistical tools were used to analyze and interpret the collected data:

Frequency Distribution and Percentage. It was used to present and analyze the profile of the respondents.

Weighted Mean. It was used to determine the effectiveness of the 7S Program using the 7S Audit Checklist towards the use of the scale below:

Scale	Interval	Qualitative Description
5	4.51 - 5.00	Highly Acceptable/ Recommended
4	3.51 - 4.50	Acceptable/ Recommended
3	2.51 - 3.50	Moderate Acceptable/ Recommended
2	1.51 - 2.50	Slightly Acceptable/ Recommended
1	1.00-1.50	Least Acceptable / Recommended

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). It was used to determine if there was a significant difference in the effectiveness of the 7S Program as assessed by the respondents when grouped according to their profile (age, gender, length of service, and highest educational attainment).

4.1 Methodology And Research Design

The Program involves 7S Structure and Composition with corresponding duties and responsibilities for the implementation of this project to ensure the successful implementation of a 7S Program. A 7S Steering Committee shall be set up to oversee and drive the performance of the 7S Program. The 7S team must map out an Implementation Plan / Proposal to determine the line-up of 7S activities and resources required to carry them out.

The study's conceptual framework adopted Coomb's systems approach, which comprises Input, Process, and Output. Figure 1 below shows the study paradigm with three diagrams aligned and connected by an arrow. The first box was Input which includes the Demographic Profile composed of age, gender, highest educational attainment, and length of service. The second box is the Process of 7S audit checklist written of Sorting, Systematizing, Sweeping, Standardizing, and Sustainability that would be used to validate the effectiveness of the 7S Program at Kasiglahan Village National High School. The third box represents the Output that describes the effectiveness of the 7S Program.

Figure 1
Conceptual Framework of the Study

4.2 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

This part includes the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data that aim to develop and prove the effectiveness of 7S Program using 7S Audit Checklist in Kasiglahan Village National High School.

5.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1.1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the teacher-respondent profiles. Based on the table, the majority of the teacher/evaluator-respondents are females (F=32 or 76.2%), where most of their age ranges from 31 to 40 years old (F=18 or 42.9%), with (6) years or more experience in the teaching profession and with earned units in the master's Program.

The data reveal that the evaluator/teacher-respondents are young professionals who are very active and enthusiastic about engaging in the 7S Program.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher and Evaluator-Respondents' Profile

Profile: GENDER	Frequency	Percentage
Male	10	23.8
Female	32	76.2
AGE		
20-30	12	28.6
31-40	18	42.9
41-50	12	28.6
More than 50 years old	0	0
LENGTH OF SERVICE		
1-5 Years	10	23.8
6-10	16	38.1
11-15	8	19
16-20	8	19
More than 20 years	0	0
HIGHEST EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT		
Bachelor Degree	14	33.3
Bachelor Degree with MA Units	20	47.3
Post Graduate	8	19.1
PhD/ EdD Degree	0	0

Table 2 Summary of 7S Validation Results as Assessed by Faculty Members and Evaluators

Indicator	Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
Sort	4.55	Highly Acceptable / Recommended
Systematize	4.63	Highly Acceptable / Recommended
Sweep	4.78	Highly Acceptable / Recommended
Standardize	4.63	Highly Acceptable / Recommended
Sustain	4.68	Highly Acceptable / Recommended

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Least Acceptable (LA), 1.50-2.50 Slightly Acceptable (SA), 2.51-3.50 Moderately Acceptable (MA), 3.51-4.50 Acceptable (A), 4.51-5.00 Highly Acceptable (HA)

Table 3. Overall Recommendation of the Respondents Towards 7S Program

Indicator	Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
Recommendation	4.66	Highly Acceptable /Recommended

Legend: 1.00-1.50 Least Acceptable (LA), 1.50-2.50 Slightly Acceptable (SA), 2.51-3.50 Moderately Acceptable (MA), 3.51-4.50 Acceptable (A), 4.51-5.00 Highly Acceptable (HA)

6.1 Summary of Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations

In terms of sorting, an average weighted mean of 4.55 with a qualitative description of “highly acceptable” was obtained. In terms of systematizing, an average weighted mean of 4.63 with a qualitative description of “highly acceptable” was obtained. In terms of sweeping, an average weighted mean of 4.78 with a qualitative description of “highly acceptable” was obtained. In terms of standardizing, an average weighted mean of 4.63 with a qualitative description of “highly acceptable” was obtained. In terms of sustainability, an average weighted mean of 4.68 with a qualitative description of “highly acceptable” was obtained.

The overall summary 7S Program in Kasiglahan Village National High School was effective as assessed by the 7S evaluator and faculty members, obtained 4.66 strengthened the claim that 7S Program is “Highly Acceptable/ Recommended” by the respondents

7.1 Conclusion

The 7S Program at Kasiglahan Village National High School is effective and highly recommended. A significant improvement is achieved; a culture of a clean working environment, Safety for teachers, a safe workplace, practicing self-discipline as a way of life, and the elimination of unnecessary stuff in the different offices.

The 7S Program in Kasiglahan Village National High School is effective and highly recommended and turned out to be a significant contributor to better-quality performance. A great improvement is achieved; a culture of a clean working environment, Safety for teachers, a safe workplace, practicing self-discipline as a way of life, and the elimination of unnecessary stuff in the different offices.

In addition, the research found that the application of the 7S Program positively impacted the school and other schools in the District of Rodriguez. The District of Rodriguez implemented the said Program. The result of

teamwork and commitment to 7S Program gives them the fulfillment of being inspired, friendly with others, and motivated, seeing the most significant impact of the school.

7.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn in this project, the following recommendations are as a result of this presented.

- The 7S Program in Kasiglahan Village National High School should maintain the school's cleanliness and orderliness.
- The 7S Program should also done in every classroom and not limited to the different offices.

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